

**Innovative Production of Samar-Based Suman with Assorted Fillings
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ABSTRACT

Gastronomists continuously modify and innovate the taste of suman by incorporating new twists with various ingredients to cater to the evolving preferences of people seeking a fusion of suman with fruits and vegetables. This study aimed to develop new methods for creating Samar-based suman with assorted fillings (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) and determine the consumer's acceptability. Using the Hedonic 9-point scale, the acceptability of the produced suman (*oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) with Assorted Fillings in Terms of Appearance Mean= 7.56, Color Mean= 7.69, Aroma Mean= 7.59, Flavor Mean= 7.56, Taste Mean= 7.78 resulting in "Like Very Much." The physicochemical properties of the assorted fillings in terms of Water Activity resulted in $a_w = 0.916 + 0.002aW$, with TSS of $68.87 + 2.78^\circ\text{Brix}$ that indicates a relatively high concentration of soluble solids, implying a pronounced sweetness and potential impact on the shelf-life and microbial stability of the product. Combining the aromatic and sweet assorted fillings (mango, munggo, and carrots) with the sticky and rich suman creates a unique gastronomic experience that could cater to consumers' evolving tastes. This promising innovation combines two staple foods in traditional Filipino cuisine with modern nutritional considerations. Incorporating carrot fillings into suman combines tradition with modern nutritional awareness.

The modification of suman using mango, mung beans, and carrots as assorted fillings represents a convergence of traditional culinary practices with modern nutritional and entrepreneurial approaches. This innovation has implications for technology and livelihood education, providing a real-world context for teaching skills related to food technology, nutrition, entrepreneurship, and cultural sustainability.

Keywords: *Development, Assorted fillings, Production of suman, Innovation*

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

Introduction

Suman is a traditional Filipino delicacy from the Visayas region, especially the province of Samar. This rice cake is crafted from glutinous rice flour, coconut milk, and sugar and is often enjoyed with various fillings such as coconut, sweet potato, or banana. This paper will delve into the innovative production of Samar-style Suman with diverse fillings. With the rising incidence of diabetes across the Philippines, including Pampanga, known as the culinary hub of the nation, it is essential to consider healthier ingredients.

Mangoes, widely appreciated in the Philippines for their sweet flavor and health benefits, are an excellent choice for those managing diabetes. Rich in vitamins A and C, potassium, and fiber, mangoes have a low glycemic index, meaning they do not cause substantial spikes in blood sugar levels. The natural sugars in mangoes are digested slowly, gradually releasing energy without causing rapid blood glucose surges. Using mangoes as a suman filling offers multiple benefits: it provides natural sweetness without added sugars, helps regulate digestion due to its fiber content, and contributes to overall health with vitamins and minerals.

Mung beans are a type of legume frequently featured in traditional Filipino dishes like adobo and sinigang. They contain essential nutrients, including protein, fiber, vitamins, and minerals. With their low glycemic index, mung beans are an excellent choice for diabetes patients. Adding mung beans to the suman filling enhances the dish's protein content, making it more filling and beneficial for blood sugar control. Additionally, their

fiber content aids digestion and prevents blood sugar spikes, while their vitamins contribute to overall health.

Carrots, well-known for their high beta-carotene content, which converts to vitamin A, are also rich in fiber, potassium, and other essential nutrients. Their low glycemic index makes them suitable for those with diabetes. Including carrots in suman fillings offers several benefits: they provide natural sweetness without extra sugars, support digestive health through their fiber content, and their vitamins and minerals support general well-being.

Creating Samar-based Suman with diverse fillings is a significant step towards achieving several Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Enhancing the appeal and marketability of suman contributes to Goal 2: Zero hunger, promoting food security and sustainable agriculture. This innovation also aligns with Goal 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, as it opens up new opportunities for local producers and entrepreneurs, fostering economic growth. Moreover, it supports Goal 12, Responsible Consumption and Production, by promoting sustainable food production and reducing waste through local ingredients.

Ensuring access to food and improving living conditions for those in need, both in rural and urban areas, is a critical aspect of social protection. This investment addresses food insecurity and promotes sustainable development (Martin, 2023).

Sustainable Development Goal 2 (SDG 2) aims to achieve food security and end all forms of hunger and poverty by 2030 as part of the Sustainable development objectives for food. The goal is to ensure that an adequate supply of nutritious food is accessible to everyone worldwide, promoting healthy lives. Strong support for sustainable agriculture and increased food production is crucial (Food and Sustainable Agriculture | Department of Economic and Social Affairs, n.d.)."

In the Philippines, the National Economic Development Authority's AmBisyon Natin 2040 envisions a future by 2040 where Filipinos experience comfort (Maginhawa) and no one suffers from hunger. Priorities of AmBisyon Natin 2040 include enhancing food production and processing (About et al. 2040—AmBisyon Natin 2040, n.d.).

Furthermore, the nation's scientific and technical endeavors should be centrally directed, led, and coordinated by the Department of Science and Technology. The HNRDA prioritized food security through initiatives such as the National Integrated Basic Research Agenda (NIBRA) and the Agriculture, Aquatic, and Natural Resources (AANR) (Decena, 2020).

Tarlac State University actively supports these international and national goals to combat hunger through food security. Both food safety and security are vital components of the University Research Agenda 2020-2023 (TSU Research Office Annual Report 2020). Sustainable food production is crucial for maintaining food security and food safety.

A sustainable way of producing food involves utilizing systems and processes that do not harm the environment, conserve natural resources and non-renewable energy, are cost-effective, ensure safety for consumers, workers, and communities, and do not compromise the needs of future generations (FutureLearn, 2022). Food preparation serves as the initial stage in sustainable food production. The term "food preparation encompasses a complex combination of techniques employed to handle, clean, cook, and preserve food to ensure its safety and palatability. Food preparation is essential for food businesses as it directly impacts the safety and quality of perishable food items. (Food Preparation: 5 Basic (but Critical) Methods for Preparing (Food et al.)."

In today's world, preparing food is easy and convenient. Many stoves are slow nowadays, so using a microwave for cooking is much easier. A meal can be cooked in no time. A dinner prepared in the oven used to take hours to prepare, but now people can utilize that time for other activities. Lunch at work can be easily and quickly prepared in the microwave.

Moreover, there is a wide range of prepackaged, convenient snacks. Lunch at the workplace can be easily and quickly prepared using a microwave. Contemporary food preparation provides a diverse selection of options. Home freezers and refrigerators allow for food preservation. Technological advancements speed up cooking, enabling individuals to prepare multiple dishes, even for a small dinner gathering. In today's world, with the availability of reheatable premade foods, people can be easily picky or selective in their choices.

Individuals living in the same household may have drastically different dietary preferences. Nowadays, it is common for people to eat out several times a week if they prefer not to cook a wide range of meals. Eating healthy has become easier than ever before. Individuals are using cooking to reduce fat and calories, which helps lower the risk of high cholesterol and heart disease. Additionally, it is now convenient to purchase rice, fruits, and vegetables, whether canned, frozen, or fresh. Many people use these nutrient-rich foods daily because they are easy to prepare. A century ago, making a low-fat smoothie in the blender using frozen fruit, ice low-fat yogurt, and canned juice would have been unimaginable.

Rice, fruits, and vegetables are essential for children's growth and well-being. However, in many Westernized nations, most children consume excessive amounts of energy-dense, high-sugar foods and insufficient quantities of these essential foods, leading to unhealthy behaviors associated with the development of non-communicable diseases (McLeod et al., 2022). according to a study referencing The World Health Organization's 2015 school-based student health survey in the Philippines, 28 percent of children aged 13 to 15 consume at least one soft drink per day, while 74 percent of children in the same age group consume less than three servings of vegetables (PDI., 2023).

To address this significant health issue, it is essential to explore creative and practical solutions that promote children's daily consumption of rice, vegetables, and fruits. In many countries, parents commonly incorporate vegetables into their children's meals for lunch, dinner, and snacks when implementing effective child-feeding practices. One

strategy to encourage people to consume more vegetables is to include them in a food format appealing to palates. Research suggests that suman with assorted fillings containing ripe mango, carrots, and munggo beans is popular among people, especially children. Studies by (Oliviero & Fogliano, 2016 Wells, 2024; da Silva, 2013; Vegetables: Tips to Encourage Children to Eat More, 2024).

Rice is a staple in meals and desserts, undeniably ingrained in people's lives. It is a fundamental necessity for survival, meeting physiological needs. Over time, Malays in the Philippines introduced various methods of preparing rice-based desserts. Rice cakes are prevalent in many cultures, especially in Asia, often gracing dining tables and bringing joy to gatherings. The researcher sees potential for innovation in combining traditional suman with new flavors. Enjoying suman can bring relaxation and satisfaction, evoking smiles and positive emotions. People are interested in familiar foods and exploring new culinary offerings in the market.

Gastronomists continuously modify and innovate the taste of suman by incorporating new twists with various ingredients to cater to the evolving preferences of people seeking a fusion of suman with fruits and vegetables.

The rice cake or suman gained popularity as a low-carb and low-fat snack in the 1980s and 1990s. Its origins in the United States trace back to the early 1900s when Alexander Pierce Anderson, a botanist at the New York Botanical Garden, developed steam-puffed rice. The term suman "holds different meanings across various countries.

The steaming method and ingredients of the suman varieties mentioned above are almost identical. Eating the same foods repeatedly can become monotonous and unsatisfying. Trying new delicacies is a refreshing experience; as the saying goes, "It is always delicious to try something new." Innovations in food preparation often lead to changes that are well-received by many. The traditional suman recipe calls for milled glutinous rice, but there may be concerns about the cleanliness of the milling equipment.

In contrast, the modern version of suman uses glutinous rice powder readily available in grocery stores, ensuring cleanliness. While the original suman includes brown sugar, some individuals, especially the elderly, prefer to avoid overly sweet foods. The updated suman recipe replaces brown sugar with honey syrup.

Because there are currently no fruit and vegetable fillings available in the market for suman, the researcher aims to address the demand by creating a new product that will cater to the cravings of most suman enthusiasts. While many enjoy eating suman to alleviate stress, they are particular about the flavor to satisfy their taste preferences. Drawing from the researcher's experience as a suman enthusiast, suman is a top-rated product that is widely purchased and consumed. Traditionally, suman is made with glutinous rice and food coloring, but the researcher intends to innovate by introducing new suman variations filled with mango, carrots, and mung beans. This new product is expected to attract the interest of suman lovers.

As the product introduces the proponent, the community becomes curious about making the new suman. Consequently, the researcher decided to name it "Suman de

Bulan," incorporating his family name into the development of this delicacy. In Pampanga, the term "Bulan" signifies the Moon. Therefore, the researcher aims to entice consumers to try this enhanced and healthy product, suggesting that while enjoying Suman de Bulan, one might feel as if they are on the surface of the Moon. This current study distinguishes itself from previous research. Moreover, it will focus on enhancing and modifying suman to increase its market acceptance.

The above-mentioned cited discourses serve as the basis for proposing this study, which aims to explore the development and acceptability of suman with assorted fillings in suman production. This study focuses on determining the development and acceptability of suman with various fillings such as ripe mango, munggo, and carrots. Additionally, it examines the consumers' acceptability in terms of appearance, color, aroma, flavor, and taste, as well as the initial product cost of the most well-received treatment of suman moron.

Mangoes (*Mangifera indica*) are tropical fruits known for their sweet, juicy flesh and are often called the "king of fruits." The Philippines is one of the major producers of mangoes, and the Carabao mango, in particular, is renowned for its sweetness and flavor. Integrating ripe mangoes into suman could improve its flavor and nutritional profile, adding vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants. Developing ripe mango fruit fillings for suman is an exciting opportunity for blending traditional Filipino dishes with contemporary food technology. Although extensive research exists on glutinous rice, mangoes, and food production technologies, additional studies are needed to fine-tune the formulation for

better taste and consumer satisfaction. This research underscores the need to grasp the properties of ingredients, advancements in food technology, and consumer preferences to create innovative food products.

This research is valuable as it combines traditional cooking methods with modern insights, offering a fresh perspective on a cherished Filipino treat. It also has practical implications for Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE), demonstrating a real-world application of food technology, nutrition, and entrepreneurship.

Conceptual Framework

This study was focused on the development of assorted fillings in the production of suman and its acceptability in terms of sensory attributes in terms of appearance, aroma, color, flavor, and taste. It also determined the physio-chemical analysis of the most acceptable fillings formulation using ripe mango fruits, carrots, and munggo regarding water activity and total soluble solids. It also aimed to determine the cost implication of the modified product with assorted fillings. The study's implications for technology and livelihood education (TLE) were also discussed.

Figure 3.
The Research Paradigm

The figure above illustrates the research procedure. This study aimed to develop Samar-based suman with assorted fillings using ripe mango fruits, carrots, and munggo.

Statement of the Objectives

This research aimed to create and assess the preparation of Samar-based suman (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) with various fillings and to gauge consumer acceptability.

In particular, the study aimed to address the following objectives:

1. To develop and formulate assorted fillings in the production of suman (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) in terms of the following fillings:
 - 1.1 Ripe Mango fruit;
 - 1.2 Munggo; and
 - 1.3 Carrots
2. To determine the consumers' acceptability of the produced suman (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) with assorted fillings in terms of:
 - 2.1 Appearance;
 - 2.2 Color;
 - 2.3 Aroma;
 - 2.4 Flavor; and
 - 2.5 Taste
3. To determine the physio-chemical properties of the assorted fillings in terms of:
 - 3.1 Water Activity (A_w), and

3.2 Total Soluble Solid (TSS)

4. To determine the initial cost product of the most acceptable suman with assorted fillings.
5. To draw the implication of the study to Technology and Livelihood Education.

Scope and Delimitation

This study was centered on describing the acceptability of suman with assorted fillings. *The participants were one hundred (100) employees, including teaching and non-teaching employees, in Systems Plus College Foundation Main Campus Balibago, Angeles City, Pampanga.* The development was identified, described, and classified based on the uniqueness of the product.

This study used a quantitative research approach and focused on developing and evaluating Samar-based suman with assorted fillings, specifically mango, mung beans, and carrots. The scope includes the formulation of recipes, sensory evaluation of produced suman, analysis of the formulation of physico-chemical properties of the fillings, cost assessment, and educational implications.

The study is limited to the sensory attributes of appearance, color, aroma, flavor, and taste, as evaluated by a panel of respondents using the Hedonic 9-point scale. The physicochemical analysis is confined to water activity and total soluble solids. The cost assessment covers the production expenses of the innovative suman recipes. The study implication for Technology and Livelihood Education will also be discussed.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-developmental research design. According to Gillaco (2014), as cited by Gana (2021), a descriptive-developmental research design involves the systematic study of designing, developing, and carefully evaluating products, innovations, processes, and products that must meet standards or criteria.

Research and Development (R&D) refers to the productive and authentic activities businesses undertake to enhance, innovate, and create new products and services. It is often a crucial stage in the development or innovation process, with the primary goal being to introduce the latest products and services to the market to boost the company's profits.

Based on Sugiyono's (2014) concept, the research and development process creates a product and evaluates its effectiveness. Gall et al. Based al. (2003:45) states that basic research and development have two primary objectives: to create a product and assess its efficacy.

This study utilized an improvement approach to create suman with assorted fillings such as mango fruit, carrots, and mung beans. Following sensory evaluation, the most well-received formulation was analyzed for its nutritional content and physio-chemical properties.

The study included 100 respondents from both teaching and non-teaching staff at Systems Plus College Foundation. Of the respondents, 12 were maintenance staff, 38 were Junior High School Teachers, 40 were Senior High School Teachers, and 10 were security

personnel at the main Balibago, Angeles City campus of Systems Plus College Foundation. The total number of employees was considered the population of the study, from which a sample was selected as the target respondents. The process of determining the sample size was explained in the sampling procedure.

Product development research encompasses product design, creation, evaluation, and marketing. It delves into the essential methods for conducting market and user research and devising a marketing strategy to promote the product to potential customers. It also pertains to monitoring the product's progression, assessing its suitability for the target audience, and determining necessary modifications to enhance its acceptance.

Developing suman with assorted fillings using ripe mangoes, carrots, and mung beans takes time and effort. It is a crucial process that guides the preparation of a product. The process of developing suman aids in the identification, comprehension, and analysis of customer wants, enabling one to respond appropriately and boost market desirability. It comprises numerous more tests that validate the product, such as loyalty.

Suman with assorted fillings using ripe mango, carrots, and mung beans is prepared differently. The seven necessary phases in the suman-making cycle include selecting, slicing, stirring, mixing, cooling, drying, and packaging. Milk, butter, sugar, milled rice powder, and sometimes optional ingredients are combined to make suman. These ingredients are usually added to a high-capacity, continuous-operation auger extruder configured with several dies to change the product's shape.

The researcher adopted the study from the original recipe (*Mama's Guide Recipe 2017*),” using its formulation, ingredients, and procedure as a foundation to create a newly formulated product. Additionally, he watched videos of other suman with fillings being made to aid in the product development process. To ensure the product acceptance by the panelists from Systems Plus College Foundation main campus in Balibago, Angeles City, Pampanga, the researcher prepared three formulations for suman with assorted fillings: mango fillings (formulation 1), carrot fillings (formulation 2) and munggo fillings (formulation 3). the main ingredients used were glutinous rice powder, ripe mango fruits, carrots, and mung beans. In contrast, butter, honey, coconut milk, fresh milk, and other ingredients were purchased at the Dau, Mabalacat public market for this study—all raw materials needed to be fresh and undamaged.

The researcher utilized ripe mango fruits, carrots, and munggo puree as the suman fillings. The researcher created suman fillings in three formulations: Formulation 1 included 150 grams of ripe mango fruits, Formulation 2 included 150 grams of carrots, and Formulation 3 included 200 grams of munggo.

The product development process involved using various materials such as a digital weighing scale, measuring cups, spoons, cooking pan, steamer, serving spoon, chopping

In the development of assorted fillings in the production of suman, the following equipment/tools were used: wok/carajay, stainless basin, mixing bowl, measuring cups, measuring spoon, measuring glass, weighing scale, strainer, ladle, blender, wood/rubber scraper, and pot steamer.

You will need some basic tools and equipment to prepare suman with various fillings using ripe mango fruits, carrots, and mung beans. At the very least, you will need a work surface, measuring spoons, cups, a knife, and a stirring and mixing utensil. Besides these essential items, there are additional tools that can make the process smoother and allow for a wider variety of suman.

When preparing suman, sanitation is of utmost importance. Ensuring that all tools and equipment used in the preparation are properly sanitized is crucial. Various methods of sanitation can be employed. In this study, all necessary materials will be thoroughly washed using clean water, sanitized, and sterilized.

The development of various fillings in the production of suman involves different processes. The three formulations were carefully performed to achieve favorable acceptability of the produced suman.

For the control procedure, pure coconut milk should be carefully strained and boiled in a cleaned wok or caraway. All necessary materials listed in Table 1 should be adequately measured using a weighing scale, measuring cups, and measuring spoons. For the white dough, measure 1 kilogram of glutinous rice and 1 cup of sugar. In a clean stainless casserole, 2 cups of boiled coconut milk, 1 cup of glutinous rice, 10 grams of star margarine, and mix well to avoid lumps.

Transfer the mixture to a cleaned wok and place it back on the gas stove. Mix it thoroughly until it becomes completely fluffy, then set aside. For the chocolate dough,

follow the same procedures and measurements as the white dough and add 80 grams of cocoa powder. Mix it well until it becomes fluffy, then set aside.

Combine 3 grams of white dough and 3 grams of chocolate dough for the wrapping dough. Gently roll the mixtures into cylinders and wrap them with banana leaves. I tied the ends with a thin strip of banana leaf as twine. Repeat the process with the remaining mixture, then place the rolled suman in a steamer basket and steam over low heat for 30 minutes.

Clean and wipe the steamed banana leaves. Form a log out of the white or plain dough. Do the same out of the chocolate dough. Align them beside each other on the banana leaf and twist the suman logs together to form a bigger one weighing 9 grams and measuring 3 inches long. Roll and wrap the suman in a banana leaf, then tie both ends of the banana leaf to secure the chocolate moron with fillings inside. Steam for 30 minutes. Once ready, unwrap the suman from the banana leaf, transfer it to a serving dish, and cool.

For the filling procedures, 1 cup (150 grams) of peeled ripe mango fruit chunks for the mango filling. Combine the mango chunks in a casserole with 1/2 cup of milk, 25 grams of butter, and 1/2 cup of honey syrup. Stir well until fluffy, then set aside.

For the mung bean filling, boil water with 1 cup of mung beans in a casserole. Remove any floating mung bean skins from the surface of the boiling water, then add 1/2

cup of milk, 1/2 cup of honey syrup, and 25 grams of butter. Mix well until it becomes fluffy, and set aside.

For the carrot filling, boil 1 cup of blended carrot vegetables in water, add 1/2 cup of milk, 1/2 cup of honey syrup, and 25 grams of butter, mix well until fluffy, and set aside.

Combine 25 grams of white dough, 25 grams of chocolate dough, and 10 grams of filling for the wrapping dough. Gently roll the mixtures into cylinders and wrap them with banana leaves, tying the ends with a thin strip of banana leaf as twine. Repeat the process with the remaining mixture, then place the rolled suman in a steamer basket and steam over low heat for 30 minutes.

One hundred consumers tested and evaluated the three treatments. The respondents were asked to taste the suman and personally fill in the scorecard to record their assessments. Before the sensory evaluation, the demographic characteristics of the consumers, including their background on the taste of suman, were collected. The sensory characteristics of modified suman were rated using a 9-point hedonic scale ranging from 1 (dislike extremely) to 9 (like extremely).

The researcher employed a random sampling technique, specifically simple random sampling, which is a form of probability sampling. This approach, known for its fairness, involves selecting a group of participants from the overall population at random, giving every individual an equal opportunity to be included. Data is then gathered from as many individuals as possible within this randomly chosen group (Pal et al., 2020).

To ascertain the appropriate number of respondents, the researcher applies the sample size formula. Sample size is a statistical measure used to decide how many observations or replicates are necessary in a sample to make valid inferences about the broader population (Sharma et al., 2020).

The formula used helps determine the sample sizes required to achieve a specified level of test power:

$$n = \left(\frac{Z_{1-\alpha/2} + Z_{1-\beta}}{ES} \right)^2$$

where:

α = determined level of significance and

$Z_{1-\alpha/2}$ = Value from the standard normal distribution holding $1-\alpha/2$ below it.

$1-\beta$ = The determined power and

$Z_{1-\beta}$ = Value from the standard normal distribution holding $1-\beta$ below it, and ES is the effect size

The researcher utilized the Hedonic Rating Test and Questionnaire developed by *Singh-Ackbarali and Maharaj (2014)* as a tool for sensory evaluation to determine the acceptability of innovative products created by undergraduate students in food science and technology at the University of Trinidad and Tobago. Among the various scales used for evaluating food acceptability among academics, David Peryam's Nine-Point Hedonic

Scale stands out as one of the most comprehensive. The researcher employed a scale of 1 to 9. The following are commonly used terms in consumer research to capture like data: 1 signifies "dislike extremely" (DE), 2 dislike "very much" (DVM), 3 "dislike moderately" (DM), 4 "dislike slightly" (DS), 5 "neither like nor dislike" (NLND), 6 "like slightly" (LS), 7 "like moderately" (LM), 8 "like very much" (LVM), and 9 "like extremely" (LE). The instrument will be the primary tool for data collection.

In the center for Food Technology and research (CFTR) laboratory of Tarlac State University, the moisture content and water activity of the newly produced goods were evaluated to determine their acceptability. Food producers must monitor the water content of their products to ensure they adhere to legal and labeling standards and maintain throughout their shelf life. Typically, suman has a water content of about 0.916 ± 0.002 post-processing, depending on the dough type and the shapes created. An object is considered dry when its internal water content equals or falls below 1% and is in equilibrium with its surroundings. A sample is put inside a tightly sealed measuring container for a water activity test. The water activity of the sample equals the relative humidity of the air surrounding the sample when the vapor pressure of the water in the substance and the water in the air approach equilibrium.

The study gathered data using questionnaires related to the study's objectives, and personal interviews were conducted with the respondents to verify the necessary information.

Consumers were asked to participate in a suman testing evaluation. After the activity, they were requested to fill out scorecards to record their assessment of the modified suman.

The scorecard questionnaires contained questions that evaluated the physical characteristics of the suman preparation and consumers' preferences when buying suman. The questionnaires were placed in sanitized and disinfected brown plastic envelopes. Maximum hygiene and health protocol standards, such as wearing a hairnet and face mask, using hand sanitizer, and checking body temperature, were observed before, during, and after the data-gathering procedure. The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS).

The materials were described. The acceptability of suman with assorted fillings, including ripe mango fruits, carrots, and munggo (mung beans) regarding appearance, color, aroma, flavor, and taste was assessed using a survey method. The physio-chemical properties, such as water content and soluble solids of the developed suman with assorted fillings, underwent food testing.

The food testing process was conducted on assorted fillings. The data was gathered through a process and formulation involving various fillings in the production of suman, which were then recorded, analyzed, and interpreted. The acceptability of the assorted fillings in the production of suman was evaluated using the Hedonic scale.

Hedonic 9-Point Scale

Rate/ Scale	Verbal Description
8.50-9.00	Like Extremely
7.50-8.49	Like Very Much
6.50-7.49	Like Moderately
5.50-6.49	Like Slightly
4.50-5.49	Neither Like nor Dislike
3.50-4.49	Dislike Slightly
2.50-3.49	Dislike Moderately
1.50-2.29	<u>Dislike Very Much</u>
1.00-1.49	Dislike Extremely

The acceptability of a meal can be measured using a scale created by David Peryam and his team at the Military Forces Quarter Master Foods and Container Institute. This scale was originally intended to assess the food preferences of military personnel. The food industry soon adopted this scale for broader use, applying it to evaluate products such as cosmetics, household items, personal care products, beverages, and food items. Consumers filled out a checklist to assess the final product, using the Hedonic Scale for this purpose. Additionally, the physio-chemical attributes, like water activity and soluble solids, were evaluated in a food testing lab to identify the most enjoyable formulation for various fillings in suman production.

The Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used to examine the differences in acceptability ratings for suman with different fillings, including ripe mangoes, carrots, and mung beans. ANOVA focused on overall variations in means rather than individual differences.

The formula for the computation of the analysis of variance is provided:

$$F = \frac{MST}{MSE}$$

where:

F = ANOVA coefficient

MST = mean sum of squares due to treatment

MSE = mean sum of squares due to errors

$$MST = \frac{SST}{P-1}$$

$$SST = \sum (n (X - \bar{x})^2)$$

where:

SST = sum of squares due to treatment

P = total number of population

n = total number of samples in a population

$$MSE = \frac{SSE}{N - P}$$

$$SSE = \sum (n - 1) S^2$$

where:

SSE = sum of squares due to error

S = standard deviation of the samples

N = total number of observations

The researcher first prepared suman with assorted fillings to achieve this, incorporating ripe mango fruits, carrots, and mung beans as flavor fillings. The researcher created three variations of suman with assorted fillings using glutinous rice powder, cocoa

powder, honey syrup, butter, fresh milk, ripe mango fruits, mung beans, and carrots. Additionally, one preparation adhered to the original suman recipe, utilizing glutinous rice flour, brown sugar, margarine, and cocoa powder as the control variable for the study.

To assess their acceptability, the researchers gathered 100 consumers to taste the three variations of suman with assorted fillings made from ripe mango fruits, carrots, and mung beans.

Additional variations of the original suman recipe were prepared. The panelists determined their preferred variant based on appearance, aroma, color, flavor, and taste. The preferred suman underwent physio-chemical analysis, and the cost implications of the modified product with assorted fillings were evaluated. Finally, the study discussed the implications of technology and livelihood education.

RESULTS, ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION

1. DEVELOPMENT AND FORMULATION OF ASSORTED FILLINGS IN THE PRODUCTION OF SUMAN (ORYZA SATIVA VAR. GLUTINOSA)

This part discusses creating and preparing various fillings such as ripe mango, mung beans, and carrots for suman (a type of sticky rice). Each filling contributes distinct flavors and nutritional advantages, which enhance the overall attractiveness of the suman.

1.1. Ripe Mango Fruit Fillings Of Suman (Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa)

Mangoes, scientifically known as *Mangifera indica*, are highly regarded tropical fruits, celebrated for their sweet and juicy flesh, earning them the title of the "king of fruits." The Philippines is a leading producer of mangoes, with the Carabao variety being particularly famous for its exceptional sweetness and flavor. Adding ripe mangoes to suman not only enhances its taste but also boosts its nutritional content. They are a rich source of vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, making them a healthy addition to your diet (Fernandez & Mendoza, 2021).

The preparation of suman with various fillings involves multiple steps, including boiling, mixing, stirring, portioning, kneading (using sheets or extrusion), and cooling. The fundamental ingredients for suman are white dough, chocolate dough, a choice of fruits or vegetables for fillings, and coconut milk.

White dough is typically made by combining glutinous rice with coconut milk and additional ingredients like honey syrup and butter.

Chocolate dough can be made by combining glutinous rice, coconut milk, cocoa powder, and other ingredients such as honey syrup and butter.

For The Suman Dough:

1. Boil coconut milk

2. Add glutinous rice powder, butter, and honey in a clean, non-stick pan. Whisk until it becomes stiff peaks. Set aside to cool.
3. In the same pan, add the glutinous rice powder mixture, butter, honey, and cocoa powder. Whisk until it becomes stiff peaks. Set aside to cool.

For the fillings:

1. Slice and boil fruits or vegetables (ripe mango fruits, mung beans, and carrots)
2. Add fresh milk and honey syrup.
3. Whisk well until it becomes puree.

Table 1
Formulation of Treatment 2- Ripe Mango Fruit Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*)

Ingredients	Quantity	Percentage
Glutinous Rice Powder	300 g	19%
Coconut Milk	600 ml (613g)	40%
Ripe mango Fruits	150 g (1 cup)	10%
Honey Syrup	200 ml (260 g)	17%
Butter	50 g	3%
Cocoa Powder	80 g	5%
Fresh Milk	100 ml (102 g)	6%
Total	1,555g	100%

Table 1 presents the results of formulations of suman with ripe mango fruit filling. The control ingredients remain the same, excluding margarine and brown sugar. The variation lies solely in the main ingredients. Accordingly, it incorporates glutinous rice powder(300g), coconut milk (600 ml), ripe peeled mango fruits (150 g), and other ingredients such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk. The formulation of Treatment

2- Ripe Mango Fruit Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa*) is a blend of the same ingredients with suman made of ripe mango fruit filling prepared for a specific purpose.

The study presents a formulation of ripe mango fruit fillings in suman, highlighting culinary innovation, nutritional enhancement, sensory appeal, and food science considerations. The fusion of traditional Filipino cuisine with the tropical flavor of mangoes enriches the gastronomic experience and offers potential health benefits. Future research could focus on optimizing the preparation techniques and extending the shelf life of the mango-filled suman.

1.2. Formulation Of Treatment 2- Munggo (*Mung Beans*) Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa*)

Mung beans are valued for their rich protein content, dietary fiber, and essential nutrients like potassium, magnesium, folate, and vitamin B6. Their low glycemic index makes them ideal for controlling blood sugar levels, and they are also recognized for their anti-inflammatory benefits (Kumar et al., 2020). Glutinous rice, primarily a source of carbohydrates, also provides some protein, fat, and micronutrients like manganese and magnesium (Juliano, 2020).

Table 2 details the recipe for suman with mung bean filling. It requires 300g of glutinous rice powder, 600 ml of coconut milk, and 200g of mung beans. The recipe also includes additional ingredients like butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk.

Table 2

**Formulation Of Treatment 2- Munggo (Mung Beans) Fillings Of Suman
(Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa)**

Ingredients	Quantity	Percentage
Glutinous Rice Powder	300 g	19%
Coconut Milk	600 ml (613g)	38%
Mung beans	1 cup (200 g)	13%
Honey Syrup	200 ml (260 g)	16%
Butter	50 g	3%
Cocoa Powder	80 g	5%
Fresh Milk	100 ml (102 g)	6%
Total	1,605g	100%

Table 2 outlines the ingredients involved in preparing suman, particularly those incorporating munggo vegetables. Mixing consistently includes vital ingredients such as glutinous rice, coconut milk, and cocoa powder. A significant step in developing suman is creating the fourth variation, which features a munggo filling.

Adding mung beans as a filling in suman not only enhances its nutritional content but also pays homage to traditional Asian culinary practices. The combination of rice's carbohydrates and the protein from beans leads to a more nutritionally balanced product in terms of macronutrients (Singh et al., 2020). This blend is a reflection of the Asian tradition of pairing rice and legumes to create a complete protein source.

**1.3. Formulation Of Treatment 3- Carrots Fillings Of Suman (Oryza Sativa
Var. Glutinosa)**

Carrots (*Daucus carota*) are renowned for their high levels of beta-carotene, a precursor to vitamin A, which plays a crucial role in maintaining vision, promoting growth, and supporting the immune system. In addition to beta-carotene, carrots are a

good source of dietary fiber, antioxidants, and essential minerals. Incorporating carrots into suman as a filling can enhance the dish's nutritional value while improving sensory aspects like flavor, color, and texture. Research has indicated that adding vegetables to traditional dishes can boost their health benefits without significantly affecting consumer preferences. Additionally, carrots are well-established as a natural colorant, imparting a vibrant orange hue to various food items.

Table 3 outlines the recipe for suman with a carrot filling. The recipe calls for 300 grams of glutinous rice powder, 600 milliliters of coconut milk, and 150 grams of carrots. The formulation includes other ingredients, such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk.

Table 3
Formulation Of Treatment 3- Carrots Fillings Of Suman (Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa)

Ingredients	Quantity	Percentage
Glutinous Rice Powder	300 g	19%
Coconut Milk	600 ml (613g)	39%
Carrots	150 g	10%
Honey Syrup	200 ml (260 g)	17%
Butter	50 g	3%
Cocoa Powder	80 g	5%
Fresh Milk	100 ml (102 g)	7%
Total	1,555g	100%

Table 3 presents the recipe for suman, a dessert made with carrots and vegetables as the main filling ingredient. The base ingredients are consistent, with only margarine and brown sugar excluded. The primary difference is the main ingredients. Table 3 includes glutinous rice powder (300g), coconut milk (600 ml), carrots and vegetables (150g), and other ingredients such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk.

The innovation in suman recipes has been the subject of recent studies, aiming to diversify the product and introduce new flavors. Suman varieties now include chocolate, fruits, and other fillings (Garcia & Reyes, 2018). These creative adaptations cater to evolving consumer tastes and the growing demand for healthier, more varied food choices. The development of Treatment 4, which features carrot fillings for suman, exemplifies this trend. It involves a delicate balance between preserving suman's traditional qualities and introducing new ingredients that attract traditionalists and a broader audience seeking healthier alternatives.

2. CONSUMERS' ACCEPTABILITY OF THE PRODUCED SUMAN (ORYZA SATIVA VAR. GLUTINOSA) WITH ASSORTED FILLINGS

Table 4 presents a comprehensive analysis of consumer preferences regarding the fillings of suman are more liked and accepted.

Table 4
Descriptive Ranking Statistics for Consumers' Acceptability of the Produced Samar-based Suman (Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa) with Assorted Fillings

Product	Appearance (Mean ± SD)	Color (Mean ± SD)	Aroma (Mean ± SD)	Flavor (Mean ± SD)	Taste (Mean ± SD)	Ranking
Mango Fillings	7.62 ± 1.80	7.57 ± 1.65	7.74 ± 1.66	7.30 ± 1.40	7.50 ± 1.48	2
Munggo Fillings	7.64 ± 1.68	7.65 ± 1.71	7.58 ± 1.70	7.74 ± 1.59	7.78 ± 1.58	1
Carrots Fillings	7.69 ± 1.59	7.69 ± 1.64	7.67 ± 1.64	7.81 ± 1.30	7.56 ± 1.76	3

Product	Appearance (Mean ± SD)	Color (Mean ± SD)	Aroma (Mean ± SD)	Flavor (Mean ± SD)	Taste (Mean ± SD)	Ranking
Traditional Suman	7.53 ± 1.68	7.74 ± 1.57	7.57 ± 1.67	7.67 ± 1.56	7.59 ± 1.71	4

Legend:

- 8.50 - 9.00: Like Extremely
- 7.50 - 8.49: Like Very Much
- 6.50 - 7.49: Like Moderately
- 5.50 - 6.49: Like Slightly
- 4.50 - 5.49: Neither Like nor Dislike
- 3.50 - 4.49: Dislike Slightly
- 2.50 - 3.49: Dislike Moderately
- 1.50 - 2.49: Dislike Very Much
- 1.00 - 1.49: Dislike Extremely

The table presents the results of a sensory evaluation of different suman with different fillings. The products evaluated were mango fillings, munggo fillings, carrots fillings, and traditional suman. The sensory attributes evaluated were appearance, aroma, flavor, and taste. The mean and standard deviation (SD) values are given for each product and each attribute. The ranking is also provided. Integrating assorted fillings into suman presents a new dimension of flavor that could significantly affect consumer acceptability. A study by Santos and Reyes (2020) on suman innovation revealed that consumers are open to new variations of traditional foods if the core characteristics are preserved and the new flavors complement the original taste

3. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE ASSORTED FILLINGS

This section discusses different fillings' physical and chemical attributes, focusing on water activity and total soluble solids. The selection of fillings can notably impact the product's physical and chemical characteristics, influencing its longevity, flavor, texture, and overall quality.

3.1. Physico-Chemical Properties Of The Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Water Activity

Water activity (a_w) is essential for assessing food products' shelf life and safety. It quantifies the free water that can support microbial growth, enzymatic reactions, and chemical processes. For suman fillings, water activity impacts their texture and the rate at which they spoil. Table 21 displays various fillings' physical and chemical properties concerning water activity, yielding $a_w = 0.916 + 0.002aW$.

Table 21
Water Activity Test Result of the Suman with Assorted Fillings

Parameters	Sample code	Requested Analysis	Result
Water Activity	SMF	Water activity	$0.916 \pm 0.002aW$

Water activity in food refers to the amount of free water available for microorganisms to grow. It's a crucial factor in food science, influencing spoilage, texture, and preservation. In suman, a traditional dish made with glutinous rice, the specific properties of the rice affect the final product. Adjusting the fillings in suman can modify these properties to achieve specific results.

The preservation of suman is significantly influenced by water activity—a level of $0.916 \pm 0.002aW$ balances microbial prevention with maintaining suman's characteristic

moist and chewy texture. Fillings can affect this water activity depending on their moisture levels and interaction with the rice. Understanding how these fillings interact with the rice is essential to ensure the modified suman remains high in quality and safe. While lower water activity can extend shelf life by reducing microbial growth, it must be managed to retain the desired sensory qualities.

3.2. Physico-Chemical Properties Of The Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Total Soluble Solid

Suman is a traditional Filipino rice cake made from glutinous rice (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*), commonly wrapped in banana leaves. This dish can be adapted with various fillings to enrich its taste. The physicochemical characteristics of these fillings are essential for evaluating the overall quality and sensory features of the altered Suman. A fundamental property is the total soluble solids (TSS), often expressed in degrees Brix ($^{\circ}$ Brix), which measures the concentration of sugars and other soluble substances in the fillings.

TSS influences the sweetness, texture, and preservation qualities of the fillings. Table 22 displays the TSS results for Suman with various fillings, as determined by physiological-chemical analysis.

Table 22
Total Soluble Solids Test Result of the Suman with Assorted Fillings

Parameters	Sample code	Requested Analysis	Result
Total Soluble Solid	Brix	Brix	68.87 $\pm$ 2.78 $^{\circ}$ Brix

The physical and chemical characteristics of the fillings used in Suman are diverse, including total soluble solids (TSS), pH, viscosity, moisture content, and flavor compounds. TSS specifically influences the sweetness, preservation, and texture of the fillings. A TSS of $68.87 \pm 2.78^\circ\text{Brix}$ suggests a high level of soluble solids, which results in significant sweetness and can affect the product's shelf-life and microbial stability.

A refractometer measures TSS, reflecting the sugar content and, thus, the sweetness of the fillings. Elevated TSS values, such as $68.87 \pm 2.78^\circ\text{Brix}$, can enhance osmotic pressure, which helps inhibit microbial growth and prolong Suman's shelf-life (Jones, 2020). Additionally, TSS directly impacts the sensory experience, including sweetness perception and mouthfeel (Smith & Johnson, 2020).

The physical and chemical properties, including TSS, are crucial in shaping the Suman's texture and flavor profile. High TSS can result in a thicker, more viscous texture, which may be favored or not, depending on consumer preferences (Lopez & Garcia, 2020). The interaction of soluble solids with other components, such as starches and lipids, also influences flavor release and perception (Kim et al., 2019).

4. PRODUCT COST OF THE MODIFIED SUMAN WITH ASSORTED FILLINGS

The primary ingredient of suman is sticky rice, which is grown in multiple regions throughout the Philippines. The expense of producing sticky rice can vary widely depending on location, farming methods, and production size. Research indicates that costs

include land preparation, seedlings, labor, irrigation, fertilizers, and pesticides. Additionally, the market price of sticky rice can fluctuate due to changes in demand and supply, seasonal variations, and economy. Adding diverse ingredients like mango, mung beans, and carrots to suman increases production expenses. These costs stem from acquiring the necessary raw materials, preparing them, and incorporating them into the suman. Mangoes, being seasonal, fluctuate in price throughout the year. While mung beans and carrots have a steadier supply, their costs can be affected by crop yields and market conditions (Garcia et al., 2022).

Table 23

Cost of Materials and Ingredients

Ingredients & Materials	Quantity	Unit	Unit Price (Php)	Total Cost (Php)
1. Glutinous Rice	2	kg	49.00	98.00
2. Coconut Milk	2	kg	35.00	70.00
3. Fresh Milk	1	ml	105.00	105.00
4. Honey Syrup	1	340 grams	230.00	230.00
5. Cocoa Powder	1	100 grams	82.50.00	82.50
6. Butter	2	400 grams	63.50	127.00
7. Mango Fruits	3 pieces	1000 grams	40.00	120.00
8. Carrots	2 pieces	400 grams	90.00	180.00
9. Munggo	1 pck	200 grams	30.00	30.00
10. Banana Leaves	2	knots	20.00	40.00
TOTAL				Php 1,082.50

Introducing assorted fillings such as mango, mung beans, and carrots into suman involves additional production costs. These costs include the procurement of raw materials, preparation, and integration into the suman. Mangoes are seasonal fruits, and their prices vary widely throughout the year. Mung beans and carrots are more stable in availability, but their costs can be influenced by agricultural yield and market demand (Garcia et al., 2022). Table 22 presents the initial cost of the modified suman under study.

5. IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY TO TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION AND OTHER STAKEHOLDERS

5.1. Technological Innovations in Food Processing

Recent progress in food technology has broadened the range of traditional recipes to align with evolving consumer tastes and nutritional needs. Food processing, preservation, and packaging innovations have played a crucial role in transforming traditional items like suman into more diverse and commercially viable products (Jones & Richardson, 2018). These advancements have also allowed local producers to reach new markets beyond their usual scope.

The adaptation of suman could have considerable effects on small-scale producers. While it may provide new market opportunities and potential for added value, it also necessitates access to advanced technologies and training (Santos & Lim, 2021). The economic implications for local communities that depend on traditional food preparation practices must be thoughtfully assessed (Dela Cruz, 2023). Integrating ingredients such as mango, mung beans, and carrots into suman reflects a trend toward innovation in food processing. This shift offers potential health benefits and aligns with

the demand for functional foods but also poses challenges related to consumer acceptance, technology adaptation, and the impact on traditional producers. Additional research is required to fully grasp the effects of these innovations on the food sector and local traditions.

5.2. Health and Nutritional Considerations in Food Modification

Incorporating mango, mung beans, and carrots into suman improves the nutritional value of this classic dish. Mangoes offer vitamins A and C, mung beans are a good source of protein and fiber, and carrots are rich in beta-carotene (Smith et al., 2019). Adding these ingredients to suman meets the rising consumer preference for healthier foods while maintaining flavor.

Enhancing suman with ingredients like mango, mung beans, and carrots can notably improve its nutritional profile by increasing its vitamin, protein, and fiber content. Nevertheless, it is essential to consider potential allergens, dietary restrictions, and the glycemic index. Ongoing research and development in food modification should balance taste, tradition, and health benefits to meet varied consumer preferences.

5.3. Livelihood Education and Entrepreneurship

Integrating new fillings into suman is a practical example of technology and livelihood education (TLE). TLE programs focus on equipping students with skills relevant to entrepreneurship and employment (Dela Cruz, 2021). By adapting suman with various fillings, TLE students can learn about product innovation, marketing, and opportunities for launching small-scale food businesses.

The evolution of traditional cuisine is ongoing, driven by globalization and shifting consumer tastes (Heldke, 2023). Introducing new fillings into suman is a way to address these changes. Ingredients like mango, mung beans, and carrots are selected for their flavor and health benefits, appealing to a health-conscious audience (Pollan, 2018). Entrepreneurs see the potential in modified suman to stand out and attract a diverse consumer base. Unique fillings allow for creating new product lines, appealing to both traditional and contemporary tastes (Porter, 2020).

Livelihood education often includes aspects of food processing and entrepreneurship. The innovation in suman production can serve as a case study in these programs, showing how traditional skills can be adapted to modern markets and business opportunities (Singh, 2022). By incorporating fillings such as mango, mung beans, and carrots, suman retains its traditional character and gains enhanced appeal and nutritional benefits. This approach exemplifies how traditional foods can adapt to contemporary preferences and market needs, opening up new possibilities for income and business growth.

5.4. Economic Implications and Market Potential

The introduction of new variants of suman carries notable economic impacts. Producers can access different market segments by broadening the range of offerings and enhancing the product's value (Garcia & Lopez, 2022). This can lead to higher earnings for farmers and entrepreneurs involved in suman's production and sale, potentially aiding rural development and economic advancement.

Incorporating diverse fillings like mango, mung beans, and carrots into suman could alter the economic dynamics of traditional Filipino foods. Although this may increase production costs, the added value could support a premium pricing approach. The market prospects for these innovative variations are vital, assuming consumer acceptance and effective marketing are achieved. Additionally, the health benefits of the new ingredients could attract health-conscious buyers, broadening the product's market appeal.

5.5. Cultural Impact and Preservation

While innovation is essential, addressing the cultural effects of altering traditional foods is equally important. Experts suggest balancing introducing new elements and preserving culinary heritage (Fernandez, 2020). When adding new variations to suman, it's crucial to do so with respect, maintaining the traditional essence while integrating new flavors and ingredients.

Suman plays a vital role in Filipino culture, often linked to celebrations and special events. It represents shared heritage and communal values, with traditional preparation techniques and recipes handed down through generations. Suman embodies the cultural continuity and identity of the Filipino people.

They incorporate mangoes, mung beans, and carrots into suman, changing its flavor and texture and boosting its nutritional value. Mangoes are rich in vitamins A and C, mung beans are high in protein and fiber, and carrots provide beta-carotene. These changes could enhance the health benefits of suman. However, while such innovations

can bring about positive outcomes like improved nutrition and sensory qualities, they raise concerns about the cultural implications of altering traditional foods. Maintaining the essence and historical significance of traditional suman and its culinary evolution is crucial.

Modifying suman with ingredients like mangoes, mung beans, and carrots illustrates the evolving nature of culinary practices and the challenges in maintaining cultural heritage. Although these changes can enhance nutritional benefits and appeal, it is essential to consider their cultural impact and ensure that traditional elements are preserved. Future research could explore how consumers perceive these modifications and their impact on cultural practices.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Summary of Findings

The salient findings of the present study are herein summarized based on the specific questions sought to be answered in this research study:

1.1 Treatment 1- Controlled Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) with main ingredients are glutinous rice powder (500g), coconut milk (1000 g), margarine (1.5 g), brown sugar (250 g), and cocoa powder (100 g). The first formulation's results can be interpreted as assembling elements to satisfy and ascertain a respondent's taste for suman. Furthermore, no single ingredient, even when applied in a sensible amount, can fully meet every requirement, whether for cleaning, beautifying, strengthening, protecting, or treating.

1.2 Formulation Of Treatment 2- Ripe Mango Fruit Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*). Mangoes (*Mangifera indica*) are tropical fruits known for their sweet, juicy flesh and are often called the "king of fruits." The control ingredients remain the same, excluding margarine and brown sugar. The variation lies solely in the main ingredients. Accordingly, it incorporates glutinous rice powder(500g), coconut milk (600 ml), ripe peeled mango fruits (600 g), and other ingredients such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk. The formulation of Treatment 2- Ripe Mango Fruit Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) is a blend of the same ingredients with suman made of ripe mango fruit filling prepared for a specific purpose.

1.3 Formulation Of Treatment 3- Munggo (*Mung Beans*) Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) Mung beans are recognized for their high protein content, dietary fibers, and essential nutrients such as potassium, magnesium, folate, and vitamin B6. In this formulation of the recipe for suman filled with mung beans. The ingredients and quantities are as follows: 500g of glutinous rice powder, 600 ml of coconut milk, and 100g of mung beans. Additional ingredients such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk were also included in the formulation.

1.4 Formulation Of Treatment 4- Carrots Fillings Of Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) Carrots (*Daucus carota*) are known for their high beta-carotene content, which is a precursor to vitamin A, essential for vision, growth, and immune function. The ingredients and quantities are 500g of glutinous rice powder, 600 ml of coconut milk, and 400g of carrots. Additional ingredients such as butter, cocoa

powder, and fresh milk are also included in the formulation of the recipe for suman, a dessert, using carrots and vegetables as the main filling ingredient. The base ingredients are consistent, excluding only margarine and brown sugar. The primary difference is the main ingredients. Table 4 includes glutinous rice powder (500g), coconut milk (600 ml), carrots (400g), and other ingredients such as butter, cocoa powder, and fresh milk.

- 2.1 Acceptability Of The Produced Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) With Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Appearance. Accordingly, using the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, the Carrots Filling has the highest Mean= 7.69, followed by Munggo with Mean= 7.64 with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.” The Appearance overall Mean= 7.56, Std. Deviation= 1.57 with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.”
- 2.2 Consumers Acceptability Of The Produced Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) With Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Color. Accordingly, using the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, the Traditional Suman has the highest Mean= 7.74 followed by the Carrot Filling with a Mean= 7.69. with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.” Further, the Color Overall Mean= 7.60, Std. Deviation= 1.64 with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.”
- 2.3 Consumers Acceptability Of The Produced Suman (*Oryza Sativa* Var. *Glutinosa*) With Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Aroma. Accordingly, using the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, Mango Filling has the highest Mean= 7.74 followed by the Carrot Filling with a Mean= 7.69. Further, the Aroma Overall Mean= 7.59, Std. Deviation 1.64 with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.”

2.4 Consumers Acceptability Of The Produced Suman (Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa)

With Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Flavor. Accordingly, using the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, the Carrot Filling has the highest Mean= 7.81 followed by the Munggo- Mug bean with a Mean= 7.74. Further, the Flavor Overall Mean= 7.56, Std. Deviation= 1.2 with verbal interpretation “Like Very much.”

2.5 Consumers Acceptability Of The Produced Suman (Oryza Sativa Var. Glutinosa)

With Assorted Fillings In Terms Of Taste. Accordingly, using the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, the Munggo- Mug Beans (Taste) has the highest Mean= 7.78 followed the Traditional Suman with a Mean= 7.59 verbal interpretation = “Like Very much.” Further, the Tast Overall Mean = 7.55, Standard deviation = 1.63, and verbal interpretation = “Like Very much.”

3.1 The physico-chemical properties of the assorted fillings in terms of Water Activity

resulted in $a_w = 0.916 \pm 0.002$. A water activity level of 0.916 ± 0.002 provides a balance between preventing microbial growth and maintaining the moist, chewy texture characteristic of suman.

3.2 The total soluble solids test result of the suman with assorted fillings was based on

physiological-chemical analysis. A TSS of $68.87 \pm 2.78^\circ$ Brix indicates a relatively high concentration of soluble solids, implying a pronounced sweetness and potential impact on the shelf-life and microbial stability of the product. The measurement of TSS is conducted using a refractometer, which indicates the sugar content and, consequently, the sweetness level of the fillings. High TSS values,

such as 68.87+2.78°Brix, can contribute to the osmotic pressure that inhibits microbial growth, thus extending the shelf-life of the Suman.

4. Suman is a traditional Filipino cake made from glutinous rice (*Oryza sativa* var. *glutinosa*) cooked in coconut milk, often wrapped in banana leaves for steaming. It is a staple kakanin (rice delicacy) in the Philippines that has been subject to various modifications over time to cater to diverse palates and preferences. The modification of suman by incorporating assorted fillings such as mango, mung beans, and carrots represents an innovative twist on the classic recipe and will require a total of Php 1,082.50 production cost. Introducing assorted fillings such as mango, mung beans, and carrots into suman involves additional production costs. These costs include the procurement of raw materials, preparation, and integration into the suman. Mangoes are seasonal fruits, and their prices vary widely throughout the year. Mung beans and carrots are more stable in terms of availability, but their costs can be influenced by agricultural yield and market demand
5. The following are the identified implications of modifying suman: Technological Innovations in Food Processing, health, and nutritional considerations in food modification, livelihood education, and entrepreneurship, economic implications and market potential, cultural impact and preservation

Conclusions

On the basis of the significant findings of this study, the herein conclusions are arrived at as follows:

- 1.1 The formulation of suman with ripe mango fruit fillings offers a promising variation of the traditional Filipino rice cake. The combination of the aromatic and sweet mango with the sticky and rich suman creates a unique gastronomic experience that could cater to consumers' evolving tastes. However, careful attention must be given to the sensory attributes, nutritional benefits, and preservation techniques to ensure the product's success in the market.
- 1.2 The formulation of mung bean fillings in suman is a promising innovation that combines two staple foods in Filipino cuisine. It could enhance the cultural diversity of Philippine cuisine and provide a healthier option than traditional suman fillings.
- 1.3 Developing carrot-based fillings for Suman blends traditional culinary practices with contemporary nutritional insights. The results indicate that this innovation could be favorably received in the market despite facing technical and cultural hurdles. Additional research and refinement are needed to improve the methods and fully evaluate consumer response.
- 1.4 Integrating carrot fillings into suman merges traditional practices with contemporary nutritional insights. This indicates that carrots can be effectively added to suman if the product maintains its sensory attributes and the health advantages are effectively communicated to consumers. Additional studies are

required to refine the recipe and evaluate how well consumers receive this novel product.

- 2.1 The results show that the visual presentation of food items, like Suman with various fillings, significantly influences how well consumers accept them. Data from the Hedonic 9-Point Scale reveal that consumers strongly prefer the look of these new Suman variations. This favorable reaction is due to the appealing visuals created by the mix of fillings, which boosts both the product's appearance and sensory attraction.
- 2.2 The results indicate that consumer approval of traditional food items can be notably improved by incorporating innovation while preserving essential sensory qualities. The addition of various fillings to Suman and the resulting color changes are favorably received by consumers, as reflected in the high average score on the Hedonic Scale. This suggests a valuable opportunity to uphold traditional cooking methods and experiment with new flavor combinations.
- 2.3 Research into consumer acceptance of Suman with various fillings, particularly its aroma, indicates a favorable response. With a mean score of 7.65 on the Hedonic 9-Point Scale, the product's scent, enhanced by ripe mango, mung beans, and carrots, was well-received and categorized as "Like Very Much." This implies that introducing new flavors and aromas to traditional dishes can be a successful approach in the food industry, especially when these innovations align with consumer expectations and improve the overall sensory experience.

- 2.4 The results indicate that consumers responded favorably to adding various fillings in suman, especially regarding taste. The high average score on the Hedonic 9-Point Scale shows that these updates to traditional foods can be effective if they are correctly implemented and the new flavors enhance the original product.
- 2.5 The results indicate that consumers respond favorably to the new suman variety with various fillings. A mean score of 7.61 on the 9-point Hedonic Scale for suman with ripe mango, mung beans, and carrots shows that consumers highly like the product. This strong level of acceptance highlights the effective blending of traditional and modern culinary techniques, meeting the taste and nutritional preferences of today's consumers.
- 5.1 Modifying traditional suman with various fillings offers a unique chance to innovate while preserving its cultural importance. Achieving a water activity level of $0.916 \pm 0.002 a_w$ is essential and can be accomplished by selecting and processing fillings meticulously to ensure safety, quality, and taste.
- 5.2 Various fillings' physical and chemical characteristics, primarily the total soluble solids (TSS), are crucial for creating modified Suman. A TSS measurement of $68.87 \pm 2.78^\circ \text{Brix}$ suggests a high concentration of soluble solids, influencing the product's sweetness, microbial stability, texture, and overall sensory qualities. Additional studies could investigate how to balance these factors to enhance the quality and appeal of modified Suman.
6. The expenses involved in producing modified suman with various fillings are complex, including costs for raw materials, processing, packaging, marketing, and

distribution. For producers, grasping these costs is essential to set competitive prices while maintaining profitability. Future studies might examine consumer preferences and willingness to pay for modified suman, offering helpful information for refining production costs and pricing approaches.

7. The adaptation of suman by incorporating mango, mung beans, and carrots as diverse fillings illustrates a blend of traditional cooking methods with contemporary nutritional and business strategies. This advancement impacts technology and vocational education by offering a practical framework for teaching skills in food technology, nutrition, business development, and cultural preservation.

Recommendations

Based on the results and the conclusions of the study, the subsequent recommendations and proposals are offered:

1. Students are encourage to actively participate in school activities, particularly those related to cooking to showcase their creativity in food preparation and innovation.
2. It is recommended that the students attend workshops focused on food innovation and the application of various cooking techniques to identify the most effective methods for creating beneficial family meals.
3. Parents, housewives, and home cooks are advise to incorporate healthy ingredients into their food preparations as a means of innovating dishes that

even their children will enjoy, such as suman with assorted fillings made of mango, carrot, and munggo.

4. TLE Teachers are encourage to incorporate activities that encourage students to innovate in creating their favorite foods.
5. Teachers and school administrators should hold seminars and workshops to helps students develop their creative cooking skills, as well as supports students in performing market activities within the school grounds, such as entrepreneurship in selling food innovation.
6. Small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) should focus on creating healthier rice cake products and innovating their food offerings
7. Future researchers might consider conducting a follow-up study to enhance the appearance, aroma, and taste of suman products to meet consumer preferences.
8. The formulation of suman with ripe mango fruit fillings offers an exciting opportunity to diversify Filipino culinary offerings and cater to contemporary consumer tastes. As such, a product could succeed by prioritizing sensory appeal, nutritional value, and effective preservation methods. Future research should focus on optimizing these aspects to develop a delightful and marketable suman product.
9. Food manufacturers and culinary innovators should explore the use of alternative, nutrient-rich ingredients in conventional rice cake recipes to produce healthier and more enticing suman items.

10. Culinary institutions and training courses should include sections on product development and sensory assessment to provide aspiring cooks and food business people with the expertise required to craft successful, consumer-oriented suman and other traditional Filipino treats.

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